
Psychological Well-Being in Students: Do Minimalist Behavior, Sustainable Consumption Behavior and Connectedness to Nature Play A Role?

Meydisa Utami Tanau¹, Sukma Noor Akbar², Halimatus Sa'diyah³, Hanifa Aisha⁴, Gt. Rynada Yuniar Noor Askiah⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5} Psychology, Universitas Lambung Mangkurat, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: Psychological well-being as part of human mental condition has a transactional relationship with the environment. Even the problem of psychological well-being decreases along with the decline in the quality of the environment. This study aims to examine the influence of happiness, gratitude, and pro-environmental behavior on minimalist behavior. This study is expected to be in line with the ULM roadmap in the field of social humanities, especially in the development of wetland environmental psychology in the South Kalimantan region. This quantitative study was designed as a cross-sectional study with 279 students as participants in South Kalimantan. Data collection used a minimalist behavior scale, a sustainable consumption behavior scale, a scale of connectedness to nature, and a scale of psychological well-being. The results of the partial analysis showed that the sustainable consumption behavior variable did not play a significant role in the psychological well-being variable ($p > 0.05$) while the minimalist behavior and connectedness to nature variables played a significant role in the psychological well-being variable ($p < 0.05$). Simultaneously, there is a role between the independent variables and the dependent variable. The results of the study are expected to contribute to scientific knowledge and application in shaping individuals, especially young adult women, to be able to maintain the psychological well-being they have through minimalist behavior and an attitude of connectedness to nature.

KEYWORDS: Psychological well-being, Minimalist Behavior, Sustainable Consumption Behavior, Connectedness to Nature

INTRODUCTION

Mental health and well-being are certainly not uncommon to discuss, this is indicated by unresolved mental health issues being re-emphasized in the theme of World Mental Health Day regarding psychological well-being, namely "Make Mental Health & Well-Being for All A Global Priority". This theme was raised with the aim of being a campaign and invitation to the world community to pay more attention and speak out about the importance of mental health and well-being and to be able to help others regarding mental health (World Health Organization, 2022).

The importance of psychological well-being is also voiced by the Indonesian government as stated in Law Number 18 of 2014 concerning Mental Health, where promotive, preventive, curative and rehabilitative efforts must continue to be carried out to pay attention to physical, mental, social, and spiritual aspects in order to achieve mentally healthy individuals (Kementrian Kesehatan RI, 2019). However, in reality this is not in accordance with what happened as stated by the Director of Prevention and Control of Mental Health Problems and Drugs who explained that mental health problems in Indonesia are related to the problem of the high prevalence of people with mental disorders that currently Indonesia has a prevalence of people with mental disorders of around 1 in 5 residents, meaning that around 20% of the population in Indonesia has the potential for mental disorders (Rokom, 2021). Based on the results of a preliminary study conducted on three people domiciled in Banjar Regency, it can be seen that the three subjects showed characteristics of low psychological well-being. This is indicated by regret or lack of acceptance of oneself in the past and present. In addition, there is also a feeling of failure in establishing good relationships with others and feeling that one is not developing. These conditions then have an impact on the lack of self-control over decision-making in managing goods, buying goods, and making the subjects not too concerned with the environment.

Mental disorders are an unresolved health problem in Indonesian society. The results of the Populix survey show that one in two Indonesians with a percentage of 52% feel that they have mental health problems. The Populix survey also revealed the symptoms of mental health experienced by respondents, namely, mood swings (26%), changes in appetite and sleep (19%), excessive fear (18%), severe fatigue (10%), feeling confused, forgetful and angry (8%). The majority of respondents 59% said that financial problems were the main trigger for mental problems experienced, the other biggest trigger factor as much as 46% was loneliness (Annur, 2022). The problem of psychological well-being is also added by the latest research from the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation, University of Washington related to the Global Burden of Disease (GBD) 2019 which states that in Indonesia

Psychological Well-Being in Students: Do Minimalist Behavior, Sustainable Consumption Behavior and Connectedness to Nature Play A Role?

mental health disorders and psychological well-being have increased over the past 30 years, namely from 1990-2019 (Nurhasim, 2022). The increase in mental health disorders and psychological well-being problems also occurred in South Kalimantan, as indicated by the increase in cases of individuals with depression in South Kalimantan. Data obtained from the South Kalimantan Health Office shows that the number of cases of depression until April 2022 reached 390 people, while in 2021 the number of depression sufferers was recorded at 338 people (Sari, 2022).

Ryff and Keyes (1995) explain that psychological well-being is a condition of individuals who can fully accept themselves, master their environment well, relate positively to others, and have feelings of happiness and satisfaction in their lives. Ryff and Keyes (1995) stated that psychological well-being has six aspects, namely, accepting oneself in the present and the past (self-acceptance), developing and growing oneself (personal growth), having the belief that life is meaningful and has a purpose in life (purpose in life), relationships with other individuals are positive (positive relationship with others), having the capacity to manage one's life and environment (environmental mastery), and the ability to determine actions independently (autonomy).

High and low psychological well-being can be influenced by social support or guidance and direction from others who have an important role in psychological well-being (Shin An & Cooney, 2006). Good social networks and maintaining the quality of relationships will reduce conflict so that it can improve psychological well-being (Wang & Kanungo, 2004). Good social networks are of course also related to good personality, where individuals who have many social networks and personal competencies such as self-acceptance, establishing harmonious relationships, good coping skills will avoid conflict and stress so that they can determine the high and low psychological well-being as well (Santrock, 2011). Furthermore, there are environmental factors that can influence the high and low psychological well-being, namely, minimalist behavior that provides benefits for individual well-being (Lloyd & Pennington, 2020). Sustainable consumption behavior that contributes to the expansion of individual potential, makes individuals live better or more meaningful lives and the level of material dependence is reduced (Carrero et al., 2020). As well as connectedness to nature which states that personal well-being is related to feelings of connectedness to nature (Leopold, 1949). Helm et al., (2019) reported that better well-being and lower levels of mental distress can be associated with less consumption and fewer possessions. Gregg (2009) stated that it is easier to adjust if one is not burdened with things such as excessive possessions, which aptly captures the concept of minimalism. Applying minimalism is also different from simply learning how to better manage one's possessions, but minimalism also involves eliminating the excess in one's life to focus on what is most important to achieve personal growth that makes them aware of their excessive consumption, its limitations in providing identity and happiness, and the sense of loss of autonomy in a consumerist culture (Rodríguez, 2018; Ugglá, 2019). According to Carrero et al. (2020) in their research, they explain that sustainable consumption behavior is encouraged as a means to ensure psychological well-being for future generations and in the short term psychological well-being is not only a consequence of sustainable consumption behavior but also a requirement for the transition to sustainability. In addition, Guillen-Royo (2019) research also stated that the positive relationship between sustainable consumption behavior and psychological well-being also occurs in psychological and physical functions. Then, according to Carrero et al. (2020) overall, aspects of sustainable consumption behavior are related to six aspects of psychological well-being, including contributing to the expansion of individual potential, making individuals live better or more meaningful lives and reducing levels of material dependence. The importance of feeling connected to nature is the initial topic of discussion in writing his findings which then argue that this relationship with nature is a key component in encouraging ecological and pro-environmental behavior (Leopold, 1949). The term connectedness to nature is interpreted as a description of a person's feelings that come from being one with nature and seeing oneself as part of nature with its affective dimension (Mayer & Frantz, 2004). The relationship between connectedness to nature and psychological well-being can be seen in conditions when someone has positive feelings towards nature, it can lead to sensitivity to feelings and support the existence of being better so that this then leads to personal psychological well-being. Supporting this research to be conducted in early adulthood Wolsko and Lindberg (2013) in their research found that there is an age pattern related to the development of connectedness to nature in individuals, namely decreasing in childhood to mid-teens, then followed by an increase until the early 20s and continuing until the end of life.

Several previous studies have found a relationship between psychological well-being and each independent variable, namely minimalist behavior, sustainable consumption behavior, and connectedness to nature. Lloyd and Pennington (2019) in their qualitative study found that minimalist behavior is related to well-being. Sustainable consumption behavior is related to psychological well-being, as in the study of Carrero et al. (2020) explained that sustainable consumption behavior is encouraged as a means to ensure psychological well-being for future generations and in the short term psychological well-being is not only a consequence of sustainable consumption behavior but also a requirement for the transition to sustainability. Kasser's (2017) study also showed that high well-being tends to follow sustainable consumption behavior because this behavior can contribute to meeting basic psychological needs for competence, attachment and autonomy. In addition, research conducted by Guillen-Royo (2019) stated that the positive relationship between sustainable consumption behavior and psychological well-being also occurs in psychological and physical functions. Research by Cervinka et al. (2012), Howell et al. (2011), and Howell et al. (2012) found that there is a positive relationship between the variable of connectedness to nature and individual well-being.

Psychological Well-Being in Students: Do Minimalist Behavior, Sustainable Consumption Behavior and Connectedness to Nature Play A Role?

Judging from previous studies, research that examines psychological well-being based on minimalist behavioral factors, sustainable consumption behavior and connectedness to nature, is still minimal in Indonesia, especially in South Kalimantan. In fact, these three variables can play a positive role in increasing psychological well-being in individuals, which is indicated by each individual being asked to try again to protect themselves and improve their mental health (World Health Organization, 2022). Therefore, this study aims to determine the dynamics of psychological well-being in students in South Kalimantan related to minimalist behavior, sustainable consumption behavior and connectedness to nature.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Psychological Well-being

Ryff and Keyes (1995) explain that psychological well-being is a condition in which an individual can fully accept themselves, master their environment well, relate positively to others, and have feelings of happiness and satisfaction in their life. Linden (2014) also defines psychological well-being as the fulfillment of an individual's potential in the process of self-realization, can function fully, meaningfulness and self-actualization. According to Sukadari and Komalasari (2020), psychological well-being can include satisfaction in life such as health, finances, social relationships, self-recreation, family, past and present comparisons, and personal comparisons with other individuals of the same age.

There are six aspects of psychological well-being, including self-acceptance, positive relationships with others, independence, mastery of the environment, life goals and personal growth (Ryff & Keyes 1995). The factors that influence psychological well-being are age, gender, social and economic status, culture, life experience, hope, gratitude and optimism (Ryff & Singer, 1996).

2. Minimalist Behavior

Minimalism is an anti-consumerist lifestyle concept that combines approaches to finding meaning in life other than consumerism (Dopierala, 2017). Minimalist behavior is defined as behavior that rejects the establishment of ideas in maximizing consumption and proposes an ethic of simplicity (Meissner, 2019). Minimalism is a planned paradigm shift in consumerism in accordance with the principles of a sustainable lifestyle and seeks to prove its effects on emotional well-being (Kang et al., 2021).

There are four aspects of minimalist behavior, namely the elimination of useless items, careful shopping, long-term use, independence (Dopierala, 2017; Kang et al., 2021). The factors that influence minimalist behavior are experiential consumption, happiness, and consumer culture (Dopierala, 2017; Gatersleben et al., 2019; Matte et al., 2021; Mourad et al., 2019).

3. Sustainable Consumption Behavior

Sustainable consumption behavior as a practice of wise consumption habits by considering post-consumption consequences for the present and future, by purchasing, using, disposing of goods and services with social and environmental concerns and avoiding excessive purchases (Quoquab & Mohammad, 2017). Sustainable consumption behavior is also defined as behavior that considers the balance of consumption to protect the rights of future generations, consider environmental welfare and to achieve a quality life (Mile, 2017).

There are three aspects of sustainable consumption behavior, namely, caring for the environment, quality of life and caring for future generations (Quoquab & Mohammad, 2017). There are two factors that influence sustainable consumption behavior, namely internal factors (consumer attitudes towards the environment, perceived responsibility for their own actions and perceived behavioral efficiency) and external factors (sustainable consumption conditions, social environment and promotion of sustainable consumption) (Korzilius, 2020).

4. Nature Connectedness Attitude

Nature connectedness attitude is a description of feelings with nature as seeing oneself as part of nature (Mayer & Frantz, 2004). Another opinion regarding nature connectedness is interpreted as an individual's belief or conviction that he or she is part of nature just like other animals and even at a more extreme stage, individuals can believe that the rights that apply to humans should also apply to plants and animals (Schultz, 2002). Nature connectedness is also defined as an increased emphasis on the importance of feeling connected to nature (more than just spending time in nature) as a potential means to develop and maintain our well-being (Cervinka et al., 2012). Nature connectedness is a unidimensional variable related to affective (Mayer and Frantz, 2004). There are three factors that influence it, namely age, gender, and personality (Di Fabio & Rosen, 2019).

METHODS

This study uses a quantitative research method. Quantitative research is a study that is compiled by focusing on the amount of data that will then be generalized (Kurniawan & Puspitaningtyas, 2016). The quantitative approach aims to test the theory objectively by examining the relationship between variables that are tested and measured using instruments and analyzed statistically

Psychological Well-Being in Students: Do Minimalist Behavior, Sustainable Consumption Behavior and Connectedness to Nature Play A Role?

(Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The research design used in this study is a cross-sectional study. Siyoto & Sodik (2015) explain that the purpose of a cross-sectional study is to study the dynamics of the relationship between factors and effects whose variables are measured only once.

The selection of the number of samples to be studied in this study was calculated using the help of G * Power software, where this device functions to calculate the strength of statistical tests of various types of tests, one of which is the correlation test. The parameters used in analyzing the number of samples to be calculated are by determining the type of analysis, significance level (α), statistical power, desired effect size and determining the tail (s) that will be used in the study.

Participants in this study were active students who were late adolescents or early adults with a total of 279 participants. The collection of trial and research data will be carried out by distributing a google form link containing the four measuring instruments used in this study. The measuring instruments used are the Ryff Psychological Well Being Scale adapted from the Ryff and Keyes scale (1995), the Minimalism Scale by Kang, et al. (2021) the Sustainable Consumption Behavior Scale by Quoquab and Mohammad (2019), and the Connectedness to Nature Scale by Mayer and Frantz (2004). Data were analyzed using multiple linear regression statistical analysis.

RESULT

Classical Assumption Test

1. Residual Normality Test

Interpretation of the residual normality test using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test can be seen based on the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value, with the prerequisite that if the value exceeds >0.05 then the data can be declared normally distributed. The results of the residual normality test indicate that the residual research data is normal where the Monte Carlo sig. value is <0.05 ($0.215 < 0.05$).

Table 1. Kolmogorov-Smirnov Residual Normality Test One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		279
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	6.22596223
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.063
	Positive	.046
	Negative	-.063
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1.056
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.215

Figure 1. Normal Plot Analysis

2. Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in the regression model there is inequality of variance from the residuals of one observation to another. The results of the heteroscedasticity test with the scatter plot as follows indicate that the research data does not experience heteroscedasticity and the regression model is feasible to use where the points are above and below the value 0 on the Y line and are spread out without forming a special pattern.

Figure 2. Scatterplot Analysis

To test heteroscedasticity, a park test is also carried out, where if sig. > 0.05, it can be stated that the data does not show symptoms of heteroscedasticity. The test results show that the research data does not experience heteroscedasticity disturbances in the three variables because the values of the three variables are > 0.005, namely the minimalist behavior variable (0.099) and sustainable consumption (0.490) and connectedness to nature (0.057).

Table 2. Heteroscedasticity Test Coefficientsa

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-1.236	2.543		-.486	.627
1 Minimalist Behavior	.083	.050	.117	1.655	.099
Sustainable Consumption	-.025	.037	-.052	-.691	.490
Connectedness to Nature	.109	.057	.137	1.915	.057

a. Dependent Variable: Psychological Well Being

3. Multicollinearity Test

This test is intended to see whether there are two or more independent variables that are linearly correlated. If this condition occurs, we will have difficulty distinguishing the influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable. To detect symptoms of multicollinearity in the research model, it can be seen from the tolerance value or the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value. The tolerance limit is > 0.10 and the VIF limit is < 10.00, so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity among the independent variables.

Psychological Well-Being in Students: Do Minimalist Behavior, Sustainable Consumption Behavior and Connectedness to Nature Play A Role?

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	21.158	4.066		5.203	.000		
Minimalist Behavior	.367	.080	.301	4.571	.000	.701	1.426
Sustainable Consumption	-.008	.059	-.010	-.141	.888	.627	1.594
Connectedness to Nature	.246	.091	.179	2.687	.008	.687	1.456

a. Dependent Variable: Psychological Well-Being

Research Hypothesis Testing

1. Partial T-Test Results

The t-statistic test basically shows how far the influence of one independent variable individually in explaining the dependent variable. This partial test is done by comparing the α (alpha) value with the p-value. If the p-value $< \alpha$ (0.05), then H0 is rejected. So it can be said that there is a partial influence between the independent variable and the dependent variable, and vice versa. The results of the analysis show that the minimalist behavior variable (0.000) and the nature connectivity variable (0.008) have a significant effect on the dependent variable, namely psychological well-being, partially ($p < 0.05$), while the sustainable consumption variable does not have a significant effect on psychological well-being partially because $0.888 > 0.005$.

Table 4. Partial T-Test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	21.158	4.066		5.203	.000
Minimalist Behavior	.367	.080	.301	4.571	.000
Sustainable Consumption	-.008	.059	-.010	-.141	.888
Connectedness to Nature	.246	.091	.179	2.687	.008

Simultaneous F Test Results

The F statistical test basically shows how far the influence of independent variables simultaneously explains the dependent variable. This simultaneous test is carried out by comparing the α (alpha) value with the p-value. If the p-value $< \alpha$ (0.05), then H0 is rejected. So it can be said that there is a simultaneous influence between the independent variable and the dependent variable, and vice versa. If the p-value $> \alpha$ (0.05), then H0 is accepted, which means that there is no influence between the independent variable and the dependent variable simultaneously. The results of the analysis show a regression significance value of 0.000, which means that there is a significant influence between independent variables simultaneously on the dependent variable ($0.000 < 0.05$). This shows that Ha is accepted and H0 is rejected, which means that there is a significant influence between minimalist behavior, sustainable consumption behavior and connectedness to nature on psychological well-being.

Table 5. Simultaneous F Test

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2121.723	3	707.241	18.049	.000 ^b
	Residual	10776.004	275	39.185		
	Total	12897.728	278			

a. Dependent Variable: Psychological Well-Being

b. Predictors: (Constant), Minimalist Behavior, Sustainable Consumption, Connectedness to Nature

DISCUSSION

The acceptance of the research hypothesis based on the results of the F test shows that minimalist behavior, sustainable consumption behavior and connectedness to nature play a role in psychological well-being. This is in line with previous findings

Psychological Well-Being in Students: Do Minimalist Behavior, Sustainable Consumption Behavior and Connectedness to Nature Play A Role?

by Lloyd & Pennington (2020) who found that implementing minimalist behavior can increase their sense of control and ability to master their environment which leads to psychological well-being. Another study conducted by Kang et al. (2021) also showed the role of minimalist behavior on psychological well-being, where the results of the study showed that individuals who implement behavior tend to feel fulfilled and sufficient for themselves and are less likely to experience psychological well-being problems such as depression. Other studies in line with research on sustainable consumption behavior also provide supporting results, namely in the study of Carerro et al. (2020) showed that overall aspects of sustainable consumption behavior are related to aspects of psychological well-being, including contributing to the expansion of individual potential, making individuals live better lives and reducing levels of material dependence. Research of Kasser's (2017) also shows that well-being tends to occur because individuals follow sustainable consumption behavior where this behavior can contribute to meeting basic psychological needs for competence, attachment and autonomy. And the connectedness with nature expressed by Mayer & Frantz (2004) with the results of their discussion stating that if an individual feels connected to nature, then they tend not to damage it, because damaging nature and its components will only harm themselves. The higher the level of individuals by enjoying activities related to nature as a recreation can also foster a greater connection with nature and gain benefits from psychological well-being (Wolsko & Lindberg, 2013).

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the research analysis on the role of minimalist behavior, sustainable consumption behavior and connectedness to nature on psychological well-being in students in South Kalimantan, it is known that the results of the partial t-test indicate that the sustainable consumption behavior variable does not play a significant role in the psychological well-being behavior variable, while the minimalist behavior and connectedness to nature variables play a significant role in the psychological well-being variable. The results of the simultaneous f test indicate that H_a is accepted, which means that there is an influence between the independent variables on the dependent variables simultaneously.

ACKNOWLEDGE

Wishes to acknowledge to the support from the Psychology Study Program, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Universitas Lambung Mangkurat.

REFERENCES

- 1) Annur, C. M. (2022). Pertumbuhan Ekonomi RI Tergolong Tinggi di G20 pada Kuartal III-2022. *Katadata.Co.Id*. <https://databoks.katadata.co.id/datapublish/2022/11/09/pertumbuhan-ekonomi-ri-tergolong-tinggi-di-g20-pada-kuartal-iii-2022%0A>
- 2) Carrero, I., Valor, C., & Redondo, R. (2020). Do All Dimensions of Sustainable Consumption Lead to Psychological Well-Being? Empirical Evidence from Young Consumers. *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics*, 33(1), 145–170. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10806-019-09818-8>
- 3) Cervinka, R., Röderer, K., & Hefler, E. (2012). Are nature lovers happy? On various indicators of well-being and connectedness with nature. *Journal of Health Psychology*, 17(3), 379–388. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1359105311416873>
- 4) Creswell, John W & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research Design Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches Fifth Edition*. SAGE Publications, Inc.
- 5) Di Fabio, A., & Rosen, M. A. (2019). Accounting for Individual Differences in Connectedness to Nature : Personality and Gender Differences. *Sustainability*, 11(6), 1693. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11061693>
- 6) Dopierała, R. (2017). Minimalism – a new mode of consumption? *Przegląd Socjologiczny*, 66, 67-83.
- 7) Gatersleben, B., Murtagh, N., Cherry, M., & Watkins, M. (2019). Moral, Wasteful, Frugal, or Thrifty? Identifying Consumer Identities to Understand and Manage Pro-Environmental Behavior. *Environment and Behavior*, 51(1), 24–49. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916517733782>
- 8) Gregg, R. B. (2009). *The value of voluntary simplicity*. The Floating Press.
- 9) Guillen-Royo, M. (2019). Sustainable consumption and wellbeing: Does on-line shopping matter? *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 229, 1112–1124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.05.061>
- 10) Guillen-Royo, M. (2019). Sustainable consumption and wellbeing: Does on-line shopping matter? *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 229, 1112–1124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.05.061>
- 11) Helm, S., Serido, J., Ahn, S.Y., Ligon, V., Shim, S., (2019). Materialist values, financial and pro-environmental behaviors, and well-being. *Young Consum.* 20 (4), 264–284.
- 12) Howell, A. J., Dopko, R. L., Passmore, H., & Buro, K. (2011). Nature connectedness : Associations with well-being and mindfulness. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 51(2), 166–171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2011.03.037>
- 13) Howell, A. J., Passmore, H., & Buro, K. (2012). Meaning in Nature: Meaning in Life as a Mediator of the Relationship

Psychological Well-Being in Students: Do Minimalist Behavior, Sustainable Consumption Behavior and Connectedness to Nature Play A Role?

- Between Nature Connectedness and Well-Being. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 14(6), 1681–1696.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-012-9403-x>
- 14) Kang, J., Martinez, C. M. J., & Johnson, C. (2021). Minimalism as a sustainable lifestyle: Its behavioral representations and contributions to emotional well-being. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 27, 802-813.
 - 15) Kasser, T. (2017). Living both well and sustainably: A review of the literature, with some reflections on future research, interventions and policy. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 375(2095). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2016.0369>
 - 16) Kementerian Kesehatan. (2019). Targetkan Indonesia Sehat Jiwa, Kemenkes Fokus pada Upaya Pencegahan. <https://sehatnegeriku.kemkes.go.id/baca/umum/20191009/0932024/targetkan-indonesia-sehat-jiwa-kemenkes-fokus-upaya-pencegahan/>
 - 17) Korzilius, H. (2020). Internal and External Determinants of Consumer Engagement in Sustainable Consumption.
 - 18) Kurniawan, A. W & Puspitaningtyas, Z. (2016). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif*. Pandiva Buku.
 - 19) Leopold, A. (1949). *A sand county almanac: With essays on conservation from Round River*. Ballantine.
 - 20) Linden, M. (2014). Promoting Resilience and Well-being with Wisdom and Wisdom Therapy.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-8669-0_5
 - 21) Lloyd, K., & Pennington, W. (2020). Towards a theory of minimalism and wellbeing. *International Journal of Applied Positive Psychology*, 5, 121-136.
 - 22) Matte, J., Fachinelli, A. C., De Toni, D., Milan, G. S., & Olea, P. M. (2021). Relationship between minimalism, happiness, life satisfaction, and experiential consumption. *SN Social Sciences*, 1(7), 1–22.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s43545-021-00191-w>
 - 23) Mayer, F. S., & Frantz, C. M. (2004). The connectedness to nature scale: A measure of individuals' feeling in community with nature. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 24(4), 503–515.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2004.10.001>
 - 24) Meissner, M. (2019). Against accumulation: lifestyle minimalism, de-growth and the present post-ecological condition. *Journal of Cultural Economy*, 12(3), 185–200. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17530350.2019.1570962>
 - 25) Mile, C. (2017). Green agriculture in hungary: The factors of competitiveness in organic farming. In *World Sustainability Series*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-45081-0_5
 - 26) Mourad, M., Cezard, F., & Joncoux, S. (2019). Eating well with zero waste: Voluntary simplicity in food practices. *Cahiers de Nutrition et de Dietetique*, 54(2), 81–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cnd.2019.02.006>
 - 27) Nurhasim, A. (2022). Data Bicara : gangguan kesehatan jiwa di Indonesia naik dalam 30 tahun terakhir, perempuan dan usia produktif lebih tinggi. <https://theconversation.com>
 - 28) Quoquab, F., Mohammad, J., & Sukari, N. N. (2019). A multiple-item scale for measuring “sustainable consumption behaviour” construct: Development and psychometric evaluation. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 31(4), 791–816. <https://doi.org/10.1108/APJML-02-2018-0047>
 - 29) Rodriguez, J., (2018). The US minimalist movement: Radical political practice? *Rev. Radical Polit. Econ.* 50 (2), 286–296
 - 30) Rokom. (2021). Kemenkes Beberkan Masalah Permasalahan Kesehatan Jiwa di Indonesia. Diakses pada 25 Januari 2023 dari <https://sehatnegeriku.kemkes.go.id>
 - 31) Ryff, C. D., & Keyes, C. L. M. (1995). The Structure of Psychological Well-Being Revisited. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 69(4), 719–727. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.69.4.719>
 - 32) Ryff, C. D., & Singer, B. (1996). Psychological Well-Being: Meaning, Measurement, and Implications for Psychotherapy Research Key Words Self-acceptance Purpose in life Positive relationships Personal growth Autonomy Environmental mastery Sociodemographic differences Vulnerability Resilien. *Psychother Psychosomatics*, 65, 14–23.
<https://www.karger.com/Article/PDF/289026>.
 - 33) Santrock, J. W. (2011). *Life-Span Development : Perkembangan Masa Hidup* (13th ed.). Erlangga.
 - 34) Sari, M. (2022). Jumlah Orang Depresi di Kalimantan Selatan Meroket di 2022. <https://banjarmasin.tribunnews.com/2022/04/16/jumlah-orang-depresi-di-kalimantan-selatan-meroket-di-2022>
 - 35) Schultz, D. (1991). *Psikologi Pertumbuhan: Model-Model Kepribadian Sehat*. Kanisius.
 - 36) Shin An, J., & Cooney, T. M. (2006). Psychological well-being in mid to late life: The role of generativity development and parent-child relationships across the lifespan. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 30(5), 410–421.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0165025406071489>
 - 37) Siyoto, S., & Sodik, A. (2015). *Dasar Metodologi Penelitian*. Literasi Media Publishing.
 - 38) Sukadari & Komalasari, M. (2020). *Pedoman Pemberdayaan Taman Lansia Berbasis Psychological Well Being*. UPY Press.

Psychological Well-Being in Students: Do Minimalist Behavior, Sustainable Consumption Behavior and Connectedness to Nature Play A Role?

- 39) Uggla, Y. (2019). Taking back control: Minimalism as a reaction to high speed and overload in contemporary society. *Sociologisk forskning*, 56(3-4), 233-252.
- 40) Wang, X., & Kanungo, R. N. (2004). Nationality, social network and psychological well-being: Expatriates in China. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 15(4-5), 775-793.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0958519042000192942>
- 41) Wolsko, C., & Lindberg, K. (2013). Experiencing Connection With Nature: The Matrix of Psychological Well-Being, Mindfulness, and Outdoor Recreation. *Ecopsychology*, 5(2), 80-91. <https://doi.org/10.1089/eco.2013.0008>
- 42) World Health Organization. (2022). World Mental Health Day 2022.
<https://www.who.int/news-room/events/detail/2022/10/10/default-calendar/world-mental-health-day-2022---make-mental-health-and-well-being-for-all-a-global-priority>